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Understanding the digital sector in Liverpool City Region

A research report for the Liverpool City Region
Civic Data Cooperative

Final Report

SQW

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1. Introduction

- 1.1** The Civic Data Cooperative (CDC) is a data stewardship programme funded by the Liverpool City Region Combined Authority (LCRCA) and the University of Liverpool. In Summer 2024, SQW was commissioned to undertake a review of the programme to support the CDC in understanding its performance and emerging impact. This report is the third and final output of the review process.

Overview of the Civic Data Cooperative

- 1.2** The CDC was established in 2020, with the aim of creating a ‘vibrant, internationally renowned civic data environment, driving economic growth in health and digital tech across the Liverpool City Region (LCR) and improving the lives of local residents – supporting better healthcare, wellbeing and job prospects’.¹
- 1.3** Over the course of delivery, the CDC’s aims, objectives and activities have evolved in response to changing patterns of demand and stakeholder feedback. In particular, a key shift in the CDC’s agenda was the move away from direct business engagement and cluster development towards data-led public service innovation. This was largely because the local data-led innovation environment was not as mature as was anticipated at the outset of the CDC programme. The updated objectives (as of early 2025) are summarised below. To deliver against these objectives, the CDC is implementing a suite of activities across three core strands: enabling technical infrastructure; participatory data stewardship; and public service innovation.
- 1.4** The CDC is sponsored through a combination of the Strategic Investment Fund (SIF) administered by the LCRCA (£5.3m) and match funding from the University of Liverpool (£6.5m). The CDC funding programme commenced in April 2020 and will end in March 2026.

CDC’s objectives

- **Connect civic organisations, industry experts, and the community** to mobilise data across the city-region to improve the lives of residents
- **Act as advocates for the better use of data**
- **Engage communities** on what’s happening with their data, data sharing and research in the region
- **Help drive research using data to create positive change** by showing organisations how best they can use data to generate insights and feed them back into the system.

Source: <https://civicdatacooperative.com/>

¹ CDC Full Business Case (2019)

Purpose and approach to this research

1.5 SQW was commissioned in Summer 2024 to undertake a review of the CDC. The two main aims of the review were to:

- undertake focused review work to inform a high-level and balanced assessment of the performance of CDC
- explore how the CDC's internal programme monitoring system and processes could be developed to ensure they are fit for purpose and draw on good practice.

1.6 The review has taken a three-phased approach. The first two phases – a scoping exercise and interim assessment - were completed in August 2024 and May 2025 respectively. Originally, the third phase of the review was to provide a final assessment of the CDC's performance. However, the focus of this phase has pivoted to provide a complementary research report on the local digital tech business base. The rationale for this was twofold: first, a more comprehensive interim assessment report was produced, including additional research such as case studies which were not originally planned at the interim stage; and second, the CDC found that the digital cluster was not as mature or as big as first anticipated, but there were gaps in the evidence base on the nature and scale of the digital tech cluster in the LCR.

1.7 Therefore, the aim of the final phase was revised to undertake a focused high-level review of the city-region's digital tech cluster. Specifically, SQW was tasked with exploring the size of the sector, its strengths and weaknesses and future growth opportunities. The findings from this research are intended to help inform the ongoing delivery of the Civic HealthTech Innovation Zone (Chi-Zone)², as well as other existing and/or future digital tech initiatives in the LCR.

1.8 This light touch research has involved the following tasks:

- A desk-based review involving two strands: (i) a review of the city-region's digital tech policy landscape; and (ii) mapping the city-region's digital sector using secondary data sources.
- Three desk-based case studies of successful digital tech clusters – Barcelona, Helsinki, and Edinburgh/Glasgow – to identify good practice from elsewhere.
- Four stakeholder consultations with the LCRCA's Chief AI Officer and Digital and Creative Cluster Lead, and representatives from two local digital tech businesses.

² Chi-Zone is a c. £10m initiatives being led by the University of Liverpool's [Civic Health Innovation Labs \(CHIL\)](#). It is funded under the city-region's Investment Zone programme which has been awarded £160m in government investment to accelerate the use of AI and other data-driven technologies to transform health and social care in the city region.

- Updating the analysis of monitoring data from the interim assessment report with the latest data formally submitted to LCRCA by the CDC covering the period up to Q3 2025/26. This analysis has been appended to the Interim Report.

1.9 The remainder of this report is structured as follows:

- Section 2: Review of the digital tech landscape
- Section 3: Qualitative reflections and learning from elsewhere
- Section 4: Recommendations.

1.10 It is also supported by two annexes: Further information on data sources and additional analysis (Annex A); and various good practice case studies (Annex B).

2. Review of the digital tech landscape

Policy context

At a national level, the UK has ambitions to become a global leader in digital and technology...

2.1 ‘Digital and Technologies’ is one of the UK Modern Industrial Strategy eight priority sectors (IS-8). In 2023, the Digital and Technologies sector contributed an estimated £207bn in GVA, accounting for 9% of the UK economy, with GVA estimated to grow by £90bn by 2035. By 2035, the vision “*is for the UK to be one of the top three places in the world to create, invest in and scale-up a fast-growing technology business*”. The underpinning Sector Plan commits to prioritising six “frontier” technologies with the greatest growth potential for the UK: advanced connectivity technologies; AI; cyber security; engineering biology; quantum technologies; and semiconductors. In order to position the UK as a global leader in the sector, the Plan sets out measures such as increasing access to finance, creating a skilled workforce, and enhancing infrastructure.³

2.2 There are also ambitions to put the UK at the forefront of global digital governance. For example, the Blueprint for Modern Digital Government (2025) sets out its six-point plan for public sector digital reform, including joining up public sector services, leveraging AI for public good, and strengthening and extending digital and data public infrastructure.⁴ Recognising cybersecurity as being foundational, the Government Cyber Action Plan (2026) - backed by £210m - sets out how the government will improve the cyber security and resilience of the government and wider public sector.⁵

.. whilst digital is also a priority growth driver for the Liverpool City Region

2.3 Digital and technologies is a key priority for the LCR. In the Metro’s Mayor 2024 Manifesto a key theme was ‘embracing the digital revolution’. This included pledges to appoint a Chief Digital Officer (latterly renamed Chief AI Officer) and establish a Data Advisory Board; expand the LCR’s digital inclusion training programme; explore the use of digital twins to aid development and improve planning; and provide the sector with the investment and training support required to support growth.⁶

2.4 Subsequently, the **Local Growth Plan (2025)** sets out the overarching ambition of ‘improving productivity’, supported by three ambitions including ‘AI for Good’ – in summary, leveraging LCR’s assets and capabilities to deliver economic growth and societal gains. **Digital and technologies is identified as a key growth driver for achieving these ambitions**, with the

³ UK Government (2025) [The UK’s Modern Industrial Strategy. Digital and Technologies Sector Plan](#)

⁴ UK Government (2025) [A blueprint for modern digital government](#)

⁵ UK Government (2026) [Government Cyber Action Plan](#)

⁶ Steve Roherham (2024) [Taking Back Our Future: Manifesto](#)

sector growth rate over the last ten years (16%) exceeding the regional and national rates (7% and 14% respectively). Three specific strategic priorities are listed:

- maximise LCR's nationally significant strengths and opportunities, and be a national pace-setter in AI and Quantum
- accelerate AI and new and emerging technology adoption across the private sector
- utilise the combination of leading digital infrastructure, assets and capabilities to drive increased clustering of digital and tech businesses in the LCR.

2.5 Leading opportunities to drive the city-region's AI and digital ambitions include creating a National Cryogenics Facility, expanding the Hartree Centre and the campus offer at Sci-Tech Daresbury more broadly, developing an AI Materials Hub for Innovation and North-West AI Skills Factory. The LCR wants to utilise these assets across the economy, and focus on 'applied tech' with the specialisms paving the way for a range of opportunities, with "scalable tech solutions transcending sectors". For example, building on the health tech and med tech cluster in the North West, and enhancing the city-region's offer in relation to FinTech, WealthTech, and LawTech (building on the strengths of LCR's Professional and Business Services).⁷

2.6 Further, LCR's Innovation Prospectus (2023), highlights the LCR's portfolio of digital assets and infrastructure strengths for potential inward investors. Alongside the CDC, this includes LCR Connect (see below), Liverpool 5G, and specialist business support such as Baltic Ventures (a pre-seed accelerator for early-stage tech companies).⁸

LCR Connect

LCR Connect is a £30m joint venture established to deliver 214 km of full-fibre, ultrafast, gigabit-capable network infrastructure across the Liverpool City Region. Launched in 2018 and completed in 2023, it is 50% owned by LCRCA and 25% each by the ITS Technology Group and NGE Concessions. By March 2024, 350 businesses had connected, with a target of 3,000 by 2030. The network offers significant cost savings - around £700 annually for businesses to access a 1 Gb circuit - while enabling digital innovation, collaboration, and cloud adoption. Businesses using LCR Connect are estimated to boost productivity by 1.2%, worth £8,100 per business annually. It is a cornerstone of LCR's economic growth strategy.

Source: LCRCA (2024) [LCR Connect Performance Review](#)

⁷ LCRCA (2025) [Liverpool City Region Growth Plan](#)

⁸ LCRCA (2023) [Liverpool City Region Innovation Prospectus](#)

Characterising LCR's digital tech cluster

- 2.7** This sub-section summarises relevant secondary data to characterise the LCR's digital sector. Four main data sources have been used – ONS, Beauhurst, The Data City and DSIT's Innovation Clusters Tool - which present materially different estimates of the size of the sector in the LCR (see Table 2-1) due to the differing methods used to identify businesses. Thus, any one given estimate should be interpreted with caution. The analysis presented below draws predominately on official ONS data, as it is considered the most reliable/accurate data source.
- 2.8** Annex A provides further information on each data source, including the methods used to identify digital tech businesses, alongside additional analysis of Beauhurst data.

Table 2-1: Estimates of digital businesses and employees in the LCR

	Number of businesses	Employment
ONS	1,805	13,000
Beauhurst – 'tracked' ⁹	344	*
Beauhurst – untracked	4,933	*
The Data City	686	10,101
DSIT Innovation Clusters	1,953	16,300

Source: ONS; Beauhurst; The Data City; DSIT
 *Beauhurst data does not present employment at the city region level

Employment in digital businesses accounts for a small proportion of overall employment with most businesses being 'micro' in size

- 2.9** In total, **2% of all jobs in the LCR are in digital firms** (13k digital jobs out of a total of 684k jobs in the city-region) - this is notably lower than the Great Britain value (4%). Just over half (52%) of the digital jobs in the LCR are in Liverpool, followed by Halton (13%) and the Wirral (11%).
- 2.10** **The vast majority of digital businesses in the LCR are 'micro'¹⁰ in size** (92% - 1,665 of 1,805 businesses) – notably the LCR does not have any 'large'¹¹ digital businesses with a head office within the geography (see Figure 2-1). A similar trend can be observed when considering turnover, with the turnover band of business skewing towards the lower end, with a median turnover of between £100k and £249k. Whilst no digital businesses are

⁹ "Tracked" means that Beauhurst gathers detailed data on the firm, including investment over time, in addition to basic Companies House data

¹⁰ A micro business has 9 or less employees

¹¹ A large business has 250 or more employees

classified as 'large', the LCR has 10 digital businesses with an annual turnover in excess of £10m (see Figure 2-2).

Figure 2-1: Distribution of LCR digital business sizes

Source: SQW Analysis of the Inter-departmental business register, 2025

Figure 2-2: Distribution of LCR digital business turnover

Source: SQW Analysis of the Inter-departmental business register, 2025

2.11 The growth of digital businesses registered in the LCR has been accelerating since the early 1980s, with a peak between 2016-2020 (Figure 2-3). Notably, between the years of 2021 and 2025, the number of registrations decreased although it is too early to consider this a trend.

Figure 2-3: Year of digital business registration

Source: SQW Analysis of Beauhurst data
 Note: Tracked firms only, includes inactive firms

2.12 Based on The Data City, the five largest ‘Digital and Technologies’ businesses by employee count and turnover¹² registered within the LCR - excluding holding companies - are listed in the table below. It is notable that the single largest company, Unilever, would not primarily be considered a digital business.

Table 2-2: Largest Digital and Technology businesses registered in the LCR

	Employee count	Turnover
Largest	Unilever PLC	Unilever PLC
Second	Arrow Business Communications Limited (ARO)	Communications Plus Ltd
Third	ITS Technology Group Limited	Arrow Business Communications Limited (ARO)
Fourth	Zifo Technologies Ltd	Zifo Technologies Ltd
Fifth	Lucid Games Limited	ITS Technology Group Limited

Source: SQW Analysis of The Data City data

¹² Declared and estimated

LCR has a higher concentration of 'Advanced Connectively Technology' businesses compared to the UK overall

2.13 The Data City data allow for a more granular analysis of the sectors that make up the businesses in the LCR, by examining the RTICs (Real Time Industrial Classification) that the digital businesses have been tagged with. Comparing the concentration of businesses within the LCR to the UK shows that in general they are less concentrated here. However, one of the sub-sectors - Advanced Connectivity Technologies¹³ - is notably more concentrated in the LCR by a factor of 1.2¹⁴ (as shown in Figure 2-4-4 below).

Table 2-3: Top three digital subsectors in the LCR

	Absolute business counts
Highest	Software Development (190)
Second highest	Telecommunications (163)
Third highest	Data Infrastructure (154)

Source: The Data City data

Figure 2-4: Concentration of Digital and Technologies subsectors

Source: SQW Analysis of The Data City data

¹³ Defined by DSIT as “technologies that enable the transmission of data in our increasingly digitised economy and society –connecting both people and things. These include technologies that make up advanced wireless systems, such as 5G and the transition to 6G, non-terrestrial networks, advanced optical networks, the growing integration of AI – and in time quantum – with communications.” (see [here](#))

¹⁴ There are 20% more of these businesses in the city region than would be predicted from the UK figures.

Digital businesses and employment are concentrated in Liverpool city centre ...

- 2.14** Using The Data City and Beauhurst data allows for the identification of individual postcodes of digital businesses (either head offices or trading locations) in the LCR. These are mapped in Figure 2-5, with a provided overlay of the DSIT identified Digital and Technologies cluster. Despite the differences in the number of locations identified, it is clear there are distinct groupings of digital businesses in: Liverpool city centre; Birkenhead to Bromborough on the Wirral; Southport; and Runcorn to Daresbury.

Figure 2-5: Digital Business locations – Beauhurst and The Data City

Source: SQW Analysis of Beauhurst and The Data City data, DSIT

- 2.15** The highest concentration of employment in the digital sector is in Liverpool city centre, with other notable concentrations around Sci-Tech Daresbury, Knowsley Industrial Park and Birkenhead (see Figure 2-6)¹⁵.

¹⁵ ONS data provides employment data down to the MSOA level across the city region

Figure 2-6: Employment in digital, 2024

Source: SQW Analysis of ONS data. Note, the two maps show the same information but presented in different ways – the map on the left shows the exact geographical distribution of the MSOAs, whilst the map on the right has each MSOA as a single hexagon, to make the map more reflective of the populations within each MSOA.

... however, compared to four comparator city regions, the LCR has a lower proportion of its working age population employed in the digital sector

- 2.16** To provide context, LCR's employment and business counts have been compared to four other combined authority areas: North East Combined Authority (NECA) geography, Glasgow City Region (GCR), West Yorkshire Combined Authority (WYCA) area, and South Yorkshire Combined Authority (SYMCA) area. These combined authority areas were chosen because they have similar sized populations to LCR.¹⁶ However, the characteristics of each area vary substantial and therefore they should be treated with care.
- 2.17** The LCR has a broadly similar concentration of digital businesses as three of the other combined authority areas (NECA, GCR and SYMCA) but a lower concentration than WYCA (Figure 2-7). This pattern has been consistent since 2010 with all city regions experiencing fluctuations simultaneously. However, Liverpool has a notably lower proportion of its working age population employed in the digital sector compared with the comparators (Figure 2-8). Taken together, these data suggest that Liverpool's digital businesses employ fewer workers than the other four city regions.

¹⁶ Ranging from 2.4m in West Yorkshire to 1.4m in South Yorkshire (ONS, 2024, Population Estimates)

Figure 2-7: Digital sector businesses, per 10,000 working age people (16-64 years)

Source: SQW analysis of ONS UK Business Counts (2025) and Population estimates (2024) data

Figure 2-8: Percentage of total employment accounted for by the digital sector

Source: SQW analysis of ONS Business Register and Employment Survey (2024)

2.18 Beahurst data convey a similar narrative. Using listings for businesses registered in each city region¹⁷ tagged with the digital 'buzzwords'¹⁸, the LCR has the lowest average number of employees of the five city regions. However, LCR businesses have the second highest average turnover – possibly suggesting the digital businesses to be particularly productive, although this productivity may come from outside of the city region (Figure 2-9).

¹⁷ This includes total employees, both inside and outside of the city regions.

¹⁸ Beahurst 'buzzwords' are proprietary sector classifications

Figure 2-9: Average turnover and employment for tracked digital businesses in each city region

Source: SQW Analysis of Beauhurst data
 Note: Average turnover and employees are estimated

Reflections and implications for the Liverpool City Region

- 2.19** The data highlight a digital sector in the LCR that is relatively small in employment terms, accounting for just 2% of all jobs compared to 4% nationally. While the number of businesses appears substantial, the overwhelming majority (92%) are micro-sized, and there are no large digital firms headquartered in the region. However, looking beyond the data there are some large, global firms with a presence in the city region including Kyndryl, Sony Interactive Entertainment, Atos, and IBM, amongst others. The data also suggest a skew towards lower turnover bands reinforcing the message that the ecosystem is dominated by small players, although the presence of a handful of firms with a turnover above £10m indicates some potential for scaling. Overall, this structure suggests more needs to be done to support digital tech scale-ups to expand within the city-region and to attract more anchor firms to the cluster in order to build critical mass and profile.
- 2.20** Comparison with the city region comparators reveals that the LCR lags in digital employment concentration, even though business density is similar, pointing to lower average firm size and possibly limited local talent absorption. However, relatively high turnover per employee suggests productivity strengths, which could be leveraged further.
- 2.21** The sector's under-concentration in most digital sub-sectors (this is often used as a proxy for specialisation), except for advanced connectivity technologies, signals a need for a clearer strategic focus and targeted intervention. However, building on current sector strengths and capabilities – such as in advanced connectivity technologies - could help to differentiate the LCR within the broader UK digital landscape.

3. Qualitative reflections and learning from elsewhere

Stakeholder perspectives

- 3.1** This sub-section summarises the feedback from the four stakeholder consultations. This includes reflections on the strengths and weaknesses of LCR's nascent digital cluster and key opportunities/priorities for the future.
- 3.2 Overall, the consultation feedback indicates that the scale of the LCR's digital cluster at present is limited.** However, it was acknowledged that there are particular strengths in areas such as HealthTech and EdTech, and an emerging strength in FinTech.
- 3.3** Three common strengths of the city-region's digital cluster were identified in the consultations:
- **LCRCA has demonstrated a commitment to developing, and investing in, digital technology in the city-region, with a particular focus on AI.** As set out in the Growth Plan (2025-35), the city region has ambitions to use 'AI for Good', with the aim of becoming a leader in responsible AI. In 2025, the LCRCA hosted an AI Summit and hired its first Chief AI Officer. The Chief AI Officer has responsibility for overseeing an 'ethical transformation of AI into a force for good in the city region'. Their work will focus primarily on three areas initially: health and social care; education; and transport. It is apparent that on the face of it, all three of these areas face primarily towards public service innovation and improvement rather than private sector-led cluster development and wealth creation.
 - **Linked to the above, there are collective aspirations amongst public, private and third sector stakeholders in the LCR to improve the quality of life of residents.** This closely aligns with the overall vision of the CDC – supporting better healthcare, wellbeing and job prospects. Stakeholders felt that this focus on social good supports engagement with innovations that have the potential to contribute towards tackling some of the city region's social and economic challenges.
 - **The city-region has the underpinning infrastructure and assets to support cluster development.** This includes universities/translational research assets (such as the University of Liverpool's Digital Innovation Factory, Materials Innovation Factory, Virtual Engineering Centre, the Sir Peter Rigby Centre for Enterprise, Civic Health Innovation Labs, and the proposed AI Materials Hub for Innovation); STFC's Hartree National Centre for Digital Innovation (which includes a new AI supercomputer); large research focused

and teaching NHS hospitals¹⁹; Baltic Ventures (designed to accelerate early-stage digital tech businesses); KQ CLICK (Liverpool's Knowledge Quarter business support network and complementary innovation facilities); LCR Connect (see Section 2); Meta-Liverpool (the world's first city-scale digital twinning and AI-enabled decision support platform); and the Office for Public Service Innovation (OPSI)²⁰. In addition, Kyndryl's new AI Innovation Lab in central Liverpool (opened in 2025) is considered an important new asset and is expected to support future job creation and skills development. More recently, two overseas AI companies (Aivion and Sepsiscan) have announced that they are establishing offices at CENTRAL TECH innovation centre in the Liverpool Knowledge Quarter.²¹ There are other major players in this space too such as Sony Interactive Entertainment including its Firesprite studio based in Liverpool. Within the Baltic Triangle area on the edge of Liverpool city centre, there is also a well-established community of digital tech micro firms and SMEs (such as Lucid Games which was acquired by Tencent's Lightspeed Studios) although additional Grade A office space is needed urgently so that businesses can take the next step on their growth journey. Other key players in the local computer games ecosystem include d3t based in Runcorn, Wushu and Ripstone in Liverpool City Centre.

3.4 Areas of weakness were more wide-ranging, but the following key points emerged:

- **The city-region's digital cluster is somewhat 'intangible'.** Identifying businesses within the sector/sub-sectors is challenging and there is no formal mechanism for businesses 'outside' the cluster to engage with businesses 'within' the cluster. One suggestion was that more activity coalescing around the specific sub-sectors (for example, like FinTech which is being facilitated by FinTech North) would be beneficial.
- **LCR lacks the presence of a blue-chip²² digital tech firm.** This makes it more challenging for the city region to develop its cluster, because it is not perceived globally as a leading hub for digital tech activity.
- **'Digital and Creative' is one of the three key growth sectors in LCR.** However, recently there has been a greater focus on the creative sector within LCRCA due to the availability of government funding. Further, in terms of supporting the development of the ecosystem, the Digital Strategy is outdated (2021-2023). This said, there are ambitions within the CA

¹⁹ The five NHS Trusts in Liverpool are currently in the process of merging into the University Hospitals of Liverpool Group (UHLG). Consultation feedback suggested this could bring opportunities in terms of data sharing and lower procurement costs.

²⁰ OPSI is a focused on encouraging data sharing and the use of new technologies such as AI to support public service innovation in the city-region. For more information see here: <https://www.liverpoolcityregion-ca.gov.uk/the-office-for-public-service-innovation>

²¹ More information can be found here: <https://sciontec.co.uk/aivion-chooses-liverpool-for-its-first-european-base/> and <https://sciontec.co.uk/latvian-medtech-spinout-expands-into-the-uk-with-sciontec/>

²² i.e. a well-established company known for their financial stability and reliable performance

to create a new post focused solely on supporting the growth and development of the digital sector.

- **Skills and recruitment challenges.** Retaining graduates in the city region with relevant skillsets can be challenging due to a general shortage of large digital tech firms with a significant volume of graduate roles. Attracting talent from outside of the LCR can also be challenging due to a (perceived) lack of opportunities in the LCR compared to other city regions.
- **Access to finance challenges for businesses, including the availability of scale-up finance and investor awareness/readiness.** This challenge is not unique to the city region, but it is more pronounced in LCR compared with some other areas (e.g. London and the South East) of the UK.

3.5 In terms of views on future priorities and opportunities for the city region, the overarching theme from the consultation feedback was that if digital tech is considered a key priority sector for LCR, it should “double down” on growing the sector and be willing to take greater risks as well as sustaining strong leadership in order to scale innovations.

3.6 The importance of improving sector networks allowing businesses to come together to share ideas and challenges was also highlighted. Finally, and related to the CDC, the importance of utilising learning and outputs from the programme going forward was cited.

Learning from elsewhere

3.7 This section examines the development of successful digital clusters internationally and within the UK to identify good practice and transferrable lessons for the LCR. Three detailed case studies - Barcelona, Helsinki, and the Edinburgh–Glasgow corridor - were selected in agreement with the client group. Short summaries are provided below, with full case studies presented in Annex B²³. Additional short examples of relevant good practice are included throughout.

²³ Note that references are provided in the full case study write-ups.

Figure 3-1: Key characteristics of the case studies

	Barcelona	Helsinki	Edinburgh & Glasgow
Population	~1.7m population	~0.7m population in city	~1.2m across two city regions
Scale of cluster	160 tech hubs employing 35k; 2,285 start-ups employing 23k	19k startup jobs; 240 firms at Maria 01 startup campus	~11k FinTech jobs; ~260 FinTech SMEs
Sub-sector focus	Industry 4.0 technologies: Business Services & Software, HealthTech, Green/EnergyTech	Deep Tech (leading startup sector), HealthTech, AI, gaming, cyber security	FinTech (primary focus), supported by wider financial services
Key policies / enabling mechanisms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1992 Catalan cluster policy ('Catalan model') • Strong FDI attraction strategy • Smart City agenda (e.g., Sentilo, CityOS) • Development of 22@ Innovation District • EU-funded AI Factory 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ambitions to be the "most functional city in the world", City Strategy 2017-21 • Ethical AI principles (2022) • Helsinki Smart Region agenda (R&D target >5% GDP) • Innovation districts and digital twin investments • Chief Digital Officer role 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic cluster management through FinTech Scotland • UK Industrial Strategy – FinTech as a high-growth sector • Financial Services Growth and Competitiveness Strategy (UK Govt) • Edinburgh & SE Scotland Innovation Plan • FinTech Research & Innovation Roadmap (2021–31)
Key assets / infrastructure	22@ District; Barcelona Supercomputing Centre (MareNostrum); 42 research centres within CERCA Network	Maria 01 startup campus (expanding to largest in Europe); 3D digital twin; Forum Virium; 6 innovation districts	Extensive financial services base; multiple FinTech-focused university centres; strong anchor institutions

Source: SQW

Barcelona

- 3.8** Barcelona hosts one of Europe's most mature and internationally recognised digital clusters, rooted in long-term innovation policy and strategic urban development. As Spain's second-largest city, with a population of approximately 1.7m in 2024, Barcelona has developed a digital ecosystem that combines large multinational technology hubs with a dense and active start-up base. The origins of this cluster can be traced back to 1992, when a new innovation and cluster policy model was introduced.

3.9 The cluster is characterised by the presence of 160 technology hubs operated by international firms, employing approximately 35,000 people and generating €2.9bn in economic activity. Companies such as IBM, Intel and Siemens have established major research and development operations in the city. Alongside this, Barcelona's start-up ecosystem employs around 23,000 people and generates €2,300m in turnover, with 2,285 start-ups, 62% of which are associated with Industry 4.0 technologies. The city is home to seven Unicorns and has particular strengths in Business Services and Software (17.9%), HealthTech (16.1%) and Green and EnergyTech (5.5%). Internationally, Barcelona ranks as the 45th largest innovation cluster globally according to the World Intellectual Property Office.

22@ Barcelona Innovation District

Photo by Héctor J. Rivas on Unsplash

3.10 A range of enabling factors underpin this success. These include the 'Catalan model' of cluster policy, strong quadruple helix collaboration, and effective Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) attraction, ranked second best in Europe. Physical and institutional assets such as the 22@ Barcelona Innovation District, the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre, 42 CERCA research centres, and a strong higher education base with 12 universities offering 645 master's programmes and 534 undergraduate programmes have further reinforced the ecosystem. Long-standing Smart City initiatives have also embedded digital capabilities within urban management.

3.11 However, the cluster faces constraints. Housing costs have risen sharply, with house prices increasing by 70% over the past decade, creating barriers to talent retention. Skills shortages also persist, with 15% of large Spanish companies reporting recruitment difficulties in 2020 and an estimated 120k technology vacancies in 2022.

Learning from elsewhere: Chattanooga, Tennessee

The city, working with its locally-owned public utility the Electric Power Board (EPB), built a city-wide, high-speed fibre optic network. This infrastructure provides universal access to some of the fastest internet speeds in the world – in 2010 the town was nicknamed "Gig City" by being the first to offer 1 Gig internet in the U.S, and there has since been continuous upgrades to the system with EPB launching a 10 Gig service in 2015 and 25 Gig service in 2022. This infrastructure has attracted inward investment to the city and supported the creation of an Innovation District centred around tech companies. LCR Connect was inspired by the municipal fibre network of Chattanooga.

Source: [Why Chattanooga | Chattanooga.gov](https://www.chattanooga.gov) and [Digital Opportunity - The Enterprise Center](#)

Helsinki

3.12 Helsinki hosts a compact but high-performing digital and tech startup cluster that is closely integrated with the city's wider smart city ambitions. As the capital of Finland, Helsinki had a population of approximately 700k in 2024, with the broader Helsinki region home to 1.6m people, representing 27% of Finland's population. Despite its relatively small size, the city has developed an internationally visible technology ecosystem.

3.13 The cluster is centred on a strong startup economy. In 2023, approximately 19k jobs in Helsinki were attributed to startups. Deep Tech is the largest startup sector, accounting for 26% of startup jobs and 30% of venture capital funding between 2022 and 2023, totalling €181 million. Helsinki has produced nine technology-based unicorns, including Rovio, Supercell, Relex Solutions and Wolt. Physical infrastructure for the ecosystem is anchored by Maria 01, a startup campus and co-working space in the city centre. Currently hosting 240 businesses across six buildings, Maria 01 is being expanded and, once completed, will be the largest startup campus in Europe.

Photo by Aleksei Zaitcev on Unsplash

3.14 The digital cluster is strongly enabled by Helsinki's smart city strategy. In 2017, the city adopted a strategy to become the "most functional city in the world," with digitalisation at its core. This has been supported through the appointment of a Chief Digital Officer, the development of a 3D digital twin of Helsinki, and the creation of Forum Virium Helsinki to support collaboration with private companies. Six designated innovation districts operate as real-world testbeds for smart city technologies, while eight principles for the ethical use of AI were introduced in 2022.

3.15 Key enabling factors include a clear policy framework, strong societal trust, and high investment in research and development. In 2022, Finland invested 2.9% of GDP in R&D, ranked seventh in Europe, and has the fifth highest global concentration of R&D researchers.

3.16 However, the ecosystem faces some challenges. Finnish tech startups commonly cite limited access to finance for scaling, compounded by a lack of a clearly structured SME support system. Cultural factors, including conservative capital deployment and limited growth ambition among firms, have also been identified as barriers to rapid scaling and long-term transformation.

Learning from elsewhere: Shenzhen, China

Over the past four decades, Shenzhen has transformed from a low-cost manufacturing hub to a high-tech innovation centre home to global tech giants such as Huawei. A set of policy tools, including building science parks (such as Shenzhen High-tech Industrial Park) and subsidising entrepreneurship and SMEs' R&D activities, has encouraged local firms to invest in innovation and cultivate their technological capability for indigenous innovation.

Source: [wipo-pub-gih-shenzhen-en-global-innovation-hotspots-innovation-ecosystems-and-catching-up-in-developing-countries-evidence-from-shenzhen.pdf](https://www.wipo.int/patent/global-innovation-hotspots-innovation-ecosystems-and-catching-up-in-developing-countries-evidence-from-shenzhen.pdf)

Edinburgh and Glasgow

3.17 The Edinburgh–Glasgow corridor forms the core of Scotland's FinTech cluster, anchored within the Scottish Central Belt.

In 2024, the combined population of the two city regions was approximately 1.2m, with the wider Central Belt home to around 2.5m people. While the region hosts a range of startup and research strengths, this cluster is most strongly associated with FinTech activity.

Photo by Humphrey M on Unsplash

3.18 The FinTech cluster is both established and growing. In 2024, the sector was estimated to employ approximately 11k people, reflecting year-on-year growth of 8%. By the end of 2025, there were around 260 FinTech SMEs, representing a 10% increase on the previous year. These firms collectively raised £1.1bn in investment during 2025, accounting for 40% of all FinTech investment raised in Scotland since 2018. The cluster is complemented by a large and diverse financial services base in Edinburgh, with approximately 1,200 financial services businesses, including major international firms such as J.P. Morgan, BlackRock, Royal London and Phoenix Group. Similarly, Glasgow is the UK's third largest financial centre, with large financial firms including Barclays, J.P. Morgan, Santander, Axa, and Zurich Insurance, alongside the government-owned Students Loans Company. The importance of the cluster was formally recognised in the Kalifa Review of UK FinTech (2020), which identified it as having the third-highest number of FinTech businesses outside London and the Pennines.

3.19 The cluster builds on a long-standing financial services heritage. Scottish banking institutions date back to the Bank of Scotland in 1695 and the Royal Bank of Scotland in 1727, with the regulatory freedoms enabled by the 1707 Act of Union supporting Edinburgh's emergence as a financial centre. The Central Belt has also been the origin of financial innovations including overdrafts, life insurance and pensions.

3.20 Key enabling factors include the presence of FinTech Scotland as a dedicated cluster organisation, a strong network of aligned research centres across universities in the Central Belt, and supportive local, national and UK-wide policy frameworks. The cluster is further supported by a small but established skills pipeline, with five of the ten UK FinTech-focused master's courses delivered in the region in 2021.

3.21 There is limited evidence specific to constraints affecting the FinTech cluster in the Scottish Central Belt, with most available insights drawn from broader challenges facing the UK FinTech and Scottish technology sectors. These include difficulties accessing finance to grow and a lack of skills.

Learning from elsewhere: Detroit, Michigan

Detroit's historic Michigan Central Station has been transformed by Ford Motor Company into the centrepiece of 'Michigan Central', a 30-acre technology and future mobility campus. The renovated station provides flexible workspaces for larger tenants and established companies. Other aspects of the campus include the Newlab - a former book depository building that was renovated into an incubator site for projects involving mobility challenges and new technology.

Source: [Michigan Central](#)

Reflections and implications for the Liverpool City Region

3.22 Across the case studies, six common enablers of success are evident, each offering important lessons for the LCR.

- **Strong, visible leadership has been crucial in each location.** This has typically been exercised through a dedicated organisation or consortium responsible for driving the cluster's development. Examples include regional and local public bodies such as the Catalan Government and Helsinki City Council, as well as independent entities like FinTech Scotland.
- **Digital cluster growth is strongest where it is supported by a stable, long-term policy environment.** Barcelona is a clear example: its digital ecosystem has been shaped by the 'Catalan Model' of cluster policy introduced in 1992, and reinforced by a sustained Smart City agenda led by the City Council since the 1990s.
- **Sector development is most effective when embedded within a broader Smart City vision.** All three case studies - Barcelona, Helsinki, and Edinburgh / Glasgow - have adopted Smart City approaches that integrate technology into urban development and provide a platform for testing, scaling and commercialising digital innovation.

- **Substantial and sustained investment in research, development and innovation has underpinned cluster growth.** The mix of public and private investment is critical, with Barcelona's success particularly influenced by its ability to attract FDI - initially catalysed by global attention and investment surrounding the 1992 Olympic Games.
- **The development of complementary assets has been essential.** Academic institutions and research centres have provided leadership, expertise and infrastructure, generated new knowledge, and created spin outs, while also supporting the skills pipeline required for digital growth.
- **Each successful cluster has focused deliberately on talent and high-growth firms from the outset.** Investment has been channelled into measures that attract, retain and develop skilled people, alongside specialist support for entrepreneurs, start-ups and spin outs, reflecting a clear, shared commitment to building a dynamic and competitive ecosystem.

3.23 Evidence on barriers to success is more limited and tends to be less sector-specific. However, two themes consistently emerged across the case studies, both of which align with challenges identified by LCR stakeholders.

- **Access to finance remains a significant constraint, particularly for early-stage and scaling businesses.** This challenge is exacerbated in digital tech by the high-risk nature of innovation and the absence of tangible collateral for many firms. Limited availability of early-stage finance can slow or stall development, reducing the likelihood of small digital firms achieving significant growth.
- **Skills shortages also present a persistent barrier, either emerging at the outset of cluster development or intensifying as demand for specialist capabilities increases.** Addressing this requires an education and training system aligned fully with current and future industry needs, complemented by measures to attract and retain talent. Ensuring a continuous and adaptive skills pipeline is therefore critical to sustaining the growth of a digital tech cluster.

4. Conclusions and recommendations

- 4.1 The Liverpool City Region (LCR) is home to approximately 1,800 digital businesses employing around 13,000 people.** Although the sector currently underperforms in scale and growth when benchmarked against other UK city regions, the overall level of activity remains significant. Importantly, digital technologies are embedded across several of the city region's established sectoral strengths - such as health and life sciences and advanced manufacturing/engineering - where they act as key enablers of innovation and productivity.
- 4.2** Some aspects of the LCR's digital tech offer and profile are strong, particularly through university-led activity and the growing capabilities at Sci-Tech Daresbury. However, stakeholder feedback suggests that the sector's full growth potential is not yet fully recognised or leveraged. The ecosystem is still emerging and remains fragmented, with limited presence of large anchor organisations. While there is a sizeable base of micro firms and SMEs, the sector lacks the scale, density and critical mass found in more established tech centres elsewhere in the UK and internationally. Low location quotients reflect limited specialisation, although it is encouraging that the sector performs more strongly on productivity measures.
- 4.3** Realising the full potential of the LCR's digital tech sector will require targeted investment and more assertive, coordinated leadership. Based on the evidence presented in this report - and SQW's tacit experience and knowledge of successful innovation cluster development - the following recommendations are proposed for consideration:

Strategic leadership and developing a compelling cluster vision

- 4.4** Building on the ambitions of the Growth Plan, partners should develop and champion a clear, coherent strategy for accelerating the growth of the city region's digital tech cluster, supported by a compelling theory of change. While there are pockets of high-quality activity, many consultees noted that opportunities to scale the sector are not being fully maximised. Fragmentation and geographic dispersion reduce the visibility, connectivity and momentum of cluster activity. A unified, long-term vision - developed collaboratively with partners - would help drive genuine clustering and improve the external profile of the LCR's digital tech strengths.
- 4.5** Three specific considerations should guide strategy development:
- **Define a clearer USP.** The city-region needs a sharper, more distinctive value proposition to differentiate its private sector-led digital tech offer in regional, national and global markets. AI and associated emerging tech is likely to feature given how pervasive it is becoming (although there will be lots of competition here), the digital end of med-tech and associated health data related opportunities, materials chemistry, supercomputing

and the digital-creative space – including computer games development, media and immersive technologies - are also likely to be strong candidates (amongst others).

- **Balance public service innovation with private sector growth.** Current strategies place a strong emphasis on public service innovation (e.g., OPSI). While important, there is a major opportunity – and need - to strengthen private sector wealth creation within the cluster. Attracting one or two global tech anchor firms should be a top priority, as this would open access to international supply chains, R&D networks, new markets and investment circles.
- **Develop a competitive offer in AI.** With AI expected to reshape every sector of the economy, the LCR must establish a credible and convincing position in this space. This includes ensuring that local businesses can access high-quality support to adopt AI safely and productively, and that the city-region builds the specialist expertise and delivery capacity needed to lead this agenda.

Leveraging the LCR's wider sectoral strengths

- 4.6** Cluster development should be closely aligned with the LCR's existing areas of competitive advantage. Strengths in health and life sciences (including infection control and bio-manufacturing), materials chemistry, advanced manufacturing/engineering (notably automotive), and high-performance and cognitive computing offer major opportunities for cross-sector innovation and should be leveraged further to stimulate growth within the digital tech cluster.

Targeting investment in the LCR's emerging / nascent digital clusters and building critical mass

- 4.7** The LCR should prioritise targeted investment in the digital technologies and enabling infrastructure that will provide long-term competitive advantage — particularly **AI, advanced computing, high-performance computing, and sector-specific innovation facilities**. Crucially, this investment must be paired with a **proactive strategy to attract one or two global tech anchor firms** to the city-region.
- 4.8** Global anchor firms act as powerful catalysts for cluster growth by:
- drawing in wider supply chains and specialist talent,
 - increasing international visibility,
 - strengthening R&D and technology partnerships, and
 - stimulating private investment through their presence and procurement power.

- 4.9** To achieve this, partners should develop a coordinated inward-investment offer that highlights the LCR's cross-sector digital tech strengths, innovation assets, and growing digital cluster locations (e.g., **Sci-Tech Daresbury, the Baltic Triangle, and CENTRAL TECH in Liverpool's Knowledge Quarter**). This offer should be backed by clear incentives, strong innovation-system support, and a compelling long-term narrative of the LCR as a location for globally significant digital capability.
- 4.10** Increased investment, specialist support, and coordinated innovation system development in these locations would help create engines of growth and provide the scale-up environment necessary to accelerate growth within the sector.
- 4.11** The LCR is home to a range of existing assets and initiatives designed to support innovation and entrepreneurship (see Section 3). However, the evidence presented earlier in this report indicates that there is an opportunity to strengthen collective efforts across the LCR – including at Sci-Tech Daresbury, the Baltic Triangle, and Liverpool's Knowledge Quarter – to enhance the city-region's digital tech entrepreneurship ecosystem, including through expanding targeted support for spin outs and student / staff start-ups from across the LCR's large HE sector.

Learning relevant lessons from elsewhere

- 4.12** Experience from leading digital clusters shows that successful ecosystems are built on sustained strategic leadership, strong anchor institutions, and deliberate long-term investment in both the enabling physical infrastructure and institutional delivery capacity.
- 4.13** For the LCR, the examples of Barcelona and Helsinki demonstrate the value of clear, long-term policy frameworks, coordinated governance, and an unambiguous innovation vision that is consistently articulated across partners. These places show that digital clusters thrive when supported by dense networks of research assets, structured collaboration across the quadruple helix, and high-quality, specialist infrastructure such as innovation centres/districts, start-up campuses and specialist assets such as supercomputing facilities. The FinTech offer across Edinburgh and Glasgow highlights the importance of a dedicated cluster organisation to convene stakeholders and drive momentum, while Chattanooga illustrates how bold investment in digital infrastructure can catalyse inward investment and stimulate new innovation activity. Shenzhen's transformation reinforces the benefits of well-targeted incentives, a strong commitment to R&D, and a supportive environment for scaling firms.
- 4.14** Together, these insights underline the need for the LCR to sharpen its strategic focus, strengthen its anchor assets, improve connectivity across its innovation landscape, and invest confidently in distinctive capabilities - particularly AI, advanced computing and place-based hubs - to build a digital tech cluster with greater scale, visibility and long-term competitiveness.

Five key recommendations for the LCR

- **Recommendation one:** Provide and sustain strong strategic leadership and articulate a clear and compelling digital tech cluster development vision. This will require a very strong focus on private sector-led growth as well as public service innovation.
- **Recommendation two:** Leverage LCR's wider sectoral strengths to drive cross-sector digital innovation.
- **Recommendation three:** Prioritise public investment (to catalyse private sector investment) in LCR's emerging and nascent digital clusters, including at Sci-Tech Daresbury, the Baltic Triangle, and Liverpool's Knowledge Quarter.
- **Recommendation four:** Develop a collective agenda and programme of entrepreneurship and incubation support across LCR's universities and innovation system to boost the supply of student/staff spin-outs and start-ups in the digital tech space.
- **Recommendation five:** Strengthen investment in distinctive digital tech capabilities, anchor-firm attraction, infrastructure and assets in the city-region.

Annex A: Further information on data sources and additional analysis

Information on data sources

- **ONS** – this is official government data used to characterise the number and size of digital firms. Digital firms have been identified by assigning businesses according to their SIC codes, as proposed by the OECD²⁴. This only includes the head office or main operating office of a business, so businesses that are based outside of the LCR but have a presence within the LCR are excluded.
- **Beauhurst** – this is a private database of businesses. Beauhurst is a database of business performance and public/private investment data for potential high-growth companies in the UK. Alongside headline data on UK registered companies, more detailed information is held on ‘tracked’ companies²⁵, including data on equity and loan investments across stages (seed, venture, growth etc.)²⁶. Beauhurst assigns industries and ‘buzzwords’ to each business through a combination of manual and automated processes. For this study, digital firms in the LCR have been classified by identifying all active ‘tracked’ businesses with at least one location in the LCR and tagged with at least one of the following four buzzwords or industries: ‘Digital and Technologies’, ‘Digital Security’, ‘Cloud Computing’, ‘Data provision and analysis’. This includes all digital businesses with at least one location within the LCR.
- **The Data City** – this is a private database of businesses. The Data City uses Machine Learning techniques to classify businesses into a number of sectors based on analysis of data including their website. For this study, digital firms have been identified by identifying all businesses tagged with ‘Digital and Technologies’, with at least one location within the LCR. This includes all digital businesses with at least one location within the LCR.
- **Department for Science and Technology (DSIT) Innovation clusters** – this is an online tool developed by DSIT to identify geographical clusters of businesses in the same sector. Digital firms have been identified using the Department for Business and Trade’s sectoral definition of the ‘Digital and Technologies’²⁷ sector. The geography of the Digital and

²⁴ [E-commerce and Internet use - Office for National Statistics](#)

²⁵ “Tracked” means that Beauhurst gathers detailed data on the firm, including investment over time, in addition to basic Companies House data

²⁶ Companies are ‘tracked’ if they meet one or more of the following ‘triggers’: the company has secured equity/venture debt investment; it meets the OECD’s definition of a scale up; it has been spun-out of a UK university or Higher Education Institution (HEI); it has completed one of the UK’s top accelerator programmes; it has completed a management buy-in/out; it has been listed on one of the UK’s top high growth lists; or has received an innovation grant (of £100k+)

²⁷ [Industrial Strategy Sector Definitions List - DBT](#)

Technologies cluster identified self-contained within the LCR. The DSIT clusters map contains a series of data about the Liverpool digital cluster that are presented in Table A-1).

Table A-1: Liverpool 'Digital and Technologies' cluster analysis

Metric	Value
Unique businesses	1953
Innovation active businesses	17.1%
Business that have engaged with UKRI	8.9%
Businesses with a published patent	2%
Total turnover	£4.6bn
Total employment	16,300
Total R&D spend used to claim tax credits	£840.8m
Total Innovate UK funding received <i>Over the last 5 years</i>	£24.7m
Total other UKRI funding received <i>Over the last 4 years</i>	£4.5m

Source: DSIT Innovation Clusters Map

Beauhurst: Additional data on currently 'tracked' organisations

High growth signals

- A.1** The primary potential high growth signal for digital firms headquartered in the LCR, resulting in them being 'tracked' on Beauhurst, was securing equity investment (64%), followed by featuring on a high growth list (28%).

Figure A-1: Beauhurst tracking reasons for digital firms (n = varies)

Source: SQW analysis of Beauhurst data
 Note: Signals are not mutually exclusive

Stage of evolution

A.2 Beauhurst assigns each 'tracked' firm a 'stage of evolution', from seed stage to death; this assessment is based on a range of data indicating risk and lifecycle stage²⁸. The 'stage of evolution' of the 'tracked' digital businesses registered in the LCR are shown in Figure A-2. Compared to digital businesses registered anywhere in the UK, the LCR has a higher proportion of firms at the latter evolution stages, including 'dead' (24%, compared to 5% nationally) and 'zombie' (4%, compared to 2% nationally), and a lower proportion of early stage firms including 'seed' (24%, compared to 35% nationally) and 'venture' (18%, compared to 24% nationally). Taken together, these data may indicate a more established and less dynamic digital cluster compared to the UK overall.

²⁸ Information on the stages can be found here: [How does Beauhurst select Stages of Evolution? - Beauhurst](#)

Figure A-2: Growth stages of 'tracked' digital firms in the LCR

Source: SQW analysis of Beauhurst data

Academic spin outs

A.3 Nine digital businesses with a registered address in the Liverpool City Region have been spun out of an academic institution, five from the University of Liverpool. These are listed in the Table A-2. Beyond the list below, only one digital business was spun out of a Liverpool based academic institution and is not currently registered in the LCR. This may indicate that the LCR is successful at retaining digital spin outs²⁹.

Table A-2: Digital spin outs in the LCR – ordered by number employees

Business	Institution spun out of
Nanoco Technologies	University of Manchester
Mycardium AI	University College London
Connected Internet Solutions	University of Liverpool
Sense AI	University of Liverpool
AI Sight	University of Liverpool
LiftUpp	University of Liverpool
Spotlight Pathology	University of Manchester
Wifi Securities	Queen's University Belfast

²⁹ Note, the one spin out was a joint spin out from another academic institution, and it is registered in the same city as the other institution.

Business	Institution spun out of
Robotiz3d	University of Liverpool

Source: SQW analysis of Beauhurst data

Annex B: Good practice case studies

Barcelona

Background and context

- B.1** Barcelona is the second-largest city in Spain and the largest city in the province of Catalonia – in 2024, the city’s population was approximately 1.7m³⁰. Within Barcelona, and more broadly across Catalonia, there is a well-established digital cluster comprising both a significant number of major international corporations and a highly active start-up ecosystem. Digital cluster development in Barcelona started in 1992 with the introduction of a new innovation model (see below).
- B.2** Barcelona hosts 160 technology hubs³¹—defined as major technology research departments of international companies—which together act as a key driver of economic growth and innovation at both regional and international levels. Collectively, these hubs employ approximately 35,000 people and generate €2.9bn in economic activity³². Major companies with technology hubs in the region include IBM, Intel and Siemens.
- B.3** Alongside these large technology hubs, Barcelona has a thriving start-up ecosystem employing around 23,000 people and generating €2,300m in turnover³³. The majority of these start-ups operate within the technology sector, with 62% of the 2,285 start-ups associated with Industry 4.0 technologies. Barcelona is home to seven ‘Unicorns’ – start-ups valued at over \$1bn³⁴. The main subsectors for startups in Catalonia are Business Services and Software (17.9%), HealthTech (16.1%) and Green and EnergyTech (5.5%)³⁵.
- B.4** According to the World Intellectual Property Office, Barcelona is the 45th largest innovation cluster globally in terms of patents filed, scientific articles published and venture capital investment³⁶. By comparison, Manchester ranks 94th, while Liverpool does not feature within the top 100.
- B.5** Barcelona benefits from substantial physical and institutional assets that underpin its digital cluster. A key asset is the 22@ Barcelona Innovation District, a 200-hectare former industrial area renovated by Barcelona City Council in the early 2000s and now functioning as a major

³⁰ InfoBarcelona (2024) The city’s population continues to grow and reaches 1.7 million

³¹ MobileWorldCapital (2025) [Tech Hubs Overview 2025](#)

³² *Ibid*

³³ Generalitat de Catalunya [Government of Catalonia] (2025) [Analysis of the startup ecosystem in Catalonia](#)

³⁴ *Ibid*

³⁵ *Ibid*

³⁶ World Intellectual Property Office (2025) [Global Innovation Index 2025](#)

innovation district³⁷. The district accounts for 21% of Barcelona's total office stock³⁸, with 31% of the more than 4,500 businesses that have operated in the district being in the technology or knowledge-based sectors³⁹.

- B.6** In terms of research infrastructure, Barcelona hosts the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre (BSC)⁴⁰, which houses MareNostrum, Spain's most powerful supercomputer. The BSC works closely with private-sector organisations based in Barcelona and beyond, including IBM and Cisco, as well as public-sector clients such as Aigües de Barcelona, the local water provider. In late 2024, it was announced that Barcelona would host one of seven EU-funded AI factories across Europe⁴¹.
- B.7** Additionally, across Catalonia, there are 42 research centres within the CERCA (Centres de Recerca de Catalunya [Research Centers of Catalonia]) Network. Many of these centres have a strong technological focus, including i2CAT, the centre for research in digital innovation, and Agrotecnio, the centre for agritech research⁴².

Enabling factors

- B.8** The success of Barcelona's digital ecosystem has been underpinned by a combination of long-standing policy decisions, institutional coordination and strategic investment. Central to this has been the 'Catalan model' which introduced a formal cluster policy in 1992 aimed at accelerating growth in micro-clusters where Catalonia already demonstrated competitive strengths. This approach built on the Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) attracted around the time of the 1992 Barcelona Olympic Games and has since been characterised by a strong emphasis on the quadruple helix model, integrating government, research institutions, businesses and society⁴³. One example of the model in practice is 'Collaboratori Catalunya', an initiative promoted by the Government of Catalonia and i2CAT (a digital research centre). The initiative is a structure for co-ordinating laboratories (across private, public and academic sectors) to boost efforts to tackle systemic challenges via digital and social innovation⁴⁴. Examples of activities they have undertaken includes running training sessions, innovation weeks and conferences, as well as facilitating the engagement between organisations⁴⁵.

³⁷ Knowledge Innovation Market – [22@ Innovation District](#)

³⁸ Cushman & Wakefield (2025) [Transparency: 22@ District, Barcelona](#)

³⁹ Patrizia (2022) [22@ - a test ground for the digital world](#)

⁴⁰ [Barcelona Supercomputing centre](#)

⁴¹ European Commission (2024) [Seven consortia selected to establish AI factories which will boost AI innovation in the EU](#)

⁴² [CERCA](#)

⁴³ ACCIÓ (2024) [Catalan Cluster Ecosystem analysis](#)

⁴⁴ Caro-Gonzalez, A. (2023) Towards a More Inclusive Triple Transition and Quadruple Helix Innovation Ecosystems: The Case of the Catalanian Col-laboratori on Health and Wellbeing Within the INTEGER Project, *Slovak Ethnology* 71 (3)

⁴⁵ [Collaboratori Catalunya](#)

- B.9** According to the fDi Intelligence European Cities and Regions of the Future report, the city's approach to the attraction of FDI is ranked as the second best in Europe⁴⁶. The early development of the 22@ Barcelona Innovation District further strengthened the ecosystem, as one of the first innovation districts globally, allowing the city to benefit from a clear first-mover advantage.
- B.10** Talent attraction has been another critical enabling factor. Catalonia is home to 12 universities offering a combined total of 645 master's programmes and 534 undergraduate programmes⁴⁷, supporting the attraction of international students and skilled graduates. Five of the top ten most commonly attended universities for Spanish founders of tech companies that have scaled are in Catalonia⁴⁸. In addition, the presence of three highly rated business schools enables the region to attract both senior leadership and skilled technical professionals⁴⁹.
- B.11** These factors have been complemented by a broader Smart City agenda led by Barcelona City Council that has existed since the late 1990s⁵⁰. Investment in initiatives such as Sentilo, a citywide sensor network collecting data on traffic, weather and noise, and CityOS, a centralised data platform enabling advanced analysis, has helped to embed digital technologies within urban management and improve the city's ability to respond to local needs. The drive for Barcelona to be a smart city is aligned with, and builds on, the strengths of the city.

Barriers

- B.12** Despite these strengths, the Barcelonan digital ecosystem faces a number of constraints. A **significant challenge is the housing crisis**, with house prices in Barcelona increasing by 70% over the past decade as a result of legal and illegal short-term lets and limited public housing development⁵¹. This has become a barrier to attracting and retaining talent, particularly for innovative early-career workers and start-up employees. **In addition, shortages in digital skills continue to affect the digital ecosystem**. In 2020, 15% of large Spanish companies reported difficulties in recruiting specialist digital talent, and in 2022 there were estimated to be 120k vacancies for skilled labour in the technology sector, indicating that skills supply has not kept pace with demand across the technology sector⁵².

⁴⁶ fDi Intelligence (2024) [European Cities and Regions of the Future 2025](#)

⁴⁷ ACCIÓ (2024) [Catalan Cluster Ecosystem analysis](#)

⁴⁸ Endeavour Insight (2022) [Mapping Spain's Tech Sector](#)

⁴⁹ IESE, ESADE and EADA

⁵⁰ Maio, J.T. and Phelps, N. (2019) The evolution of smart city: case studies of Barcelona, Spain and Helsinki, Finland

⁵¹ Kassam, A. (2025) [Europe's housing costs akin to 'new pandemic', warns Barcelona mayor](#)

⁵² Digitales_ (2024) [Anatomía de la brecha de talento tecnológico](#)

Helsinki

Background and context

- B.13** Helsinki is the capital of Finland. In 2024, Helsinki city had a population of approximately 700k, comparable in size to Leeds in the UK (810k as of the 2021 Census), whilst the broader Helsinki region had a population of 1.6m – 27% of the population of Finland⁵³.
- B.14** Helsinki has developed a strong startup ecosystem. In 2023, approximately 19k jobs in the city were attributed to startups. The largest startup sector is Deep Tech, accounting for 26% of startup jobs and 30% of venture capital funding between 2022 and 2023, totalling €181 million⁵⁴. Helsinki has produced nine unicorns, all technology-based, including Rovio and Supercell (mobile gaming companies), Relex Solutions (retail software), and Wolt (food delivery)⁵⁵.
- B.15** The city is currently expanding Maria 01, a startup campus and co-working space located in the city centre. Once completed, it will be the largest startup campus in Europe⁵⁶. At present, Maria 01 hosts 240 businesses across six buildings, many of which operate in technology-focused sectors such as AI, HealthTech, gaming, and cyber security.
- B.16** The digital cluster is closely aligned with a city-wide smart city initiative. In 2017, Helsinki adopted a new city strategy with the ambition of becoming the “most functional city in the world,” explicitly aiming to be the city that makes the best use of digitalisation⁵⁷. In support of this strategy, Helsinki has implemented several initiatives, including:
- the appointment of a Chief Digital Officer to ensure the systematic application of digital transformation across the city⁵⁸
 - the development of a 3D digital twin of Helsinki, enabling experimental uses of civic data such as testing traffic planning and proposed construction projects⁵⁹
 - the establishment of Forum Virium Helsinki, an independent not-for-profit organisation that collaborates with private companies to develop new innovations for the city⁶⁰.

⁵³ City of Helsinki (2025) [Helsinki facts and figures 2025](#)

⁵⁴ Business Helsinki; Dealroom (2023) [Helsinki startup ecosystem 2023](#)

⁵⁵ Business Helsinki; Dealroom (2025) [Companies dashboard](#).

⁵⁶ Savage, M. (2025) [Finland's bid to win Europe's start-up crown](#).

⁵⁷ Helsinki (2017) [The Most Functional City in the world: Helsinki city strategy 2017-2021](#).

⁵⁸ Hämäläinen, M (2020) A Framework for a Smart City Design : Digital Transformation in the Helsinki Smart City

⁵⁹ City of Helsinki (Unknown) [Data brings benefits](#)

⁶⁰ Hämäläinen, M (2020) A Framework for a Smart City Design : Digital Transformation in the Helsinki Smart City

- B.17** The smart city strategy is framed around improving residents' quality of life. In 2022, Helsinki introduced eight principles for the ethical use of AI, aimed at minimising risks while encouraging the adoption of AI and innovative technologies within the public sector⁶¹.
- B.18** As part of this city-wide initiative, Helsinki hosts six designated innovation districts⁶². These areas - ranging from a major transport hub to an island off the Helsinki peninsula and high-density residential neighbourhoods - are used as testbeds for smart city technologies. The districts reduce barriers for businesses to pilot and demonstrate new solutions, accelerating development and allowing technologies to be tested across a range of urban contexts.

Enabling factors

- B.19 Helsinki has established a strong policy framework to support the development of its tech cluster and smart city agenda.** The Helsinki Smart Region report⁶³, published in 2022, clearly states the city's ambitions to 2030, including a target for over 5% of GDP generated in the Helsinki region to be invested in research and development.
- B.20** The Finnish innovation system, of which Helsinki is a central component, benefits from **political stability and high levels of societal trust**, providing businesses with confidence to invest. Finland also has a **highly skilled workforce**, including in ICT⁶⁴, underpinned by a strong education system⁶⁵.
- B.21 Finland demonstrates a strong commitment to R&D and innovation.** According to UNESCO data from 2023, Finland invested 2.9% of GDP in R&D in 2022, slightly higher than the UK and the seventh highest level in Europe⁶⁶. Finland also has the fifth highest concentration of researchers working in R&D globally⁶⁷. An EU study published in 2024⁶⁸ found that Finland ranked fourth in Europe for the concentration of organisations participating in Erasmus+ Knowledge Alliances, which bring together businesses and academic institutions to address shared challenges.

Limiting factors

- B.22 The most commonly cited barrier for Finnish tech startups is limited access to finance for scaling⁶⁹.** Compared to many other European economies, Finland lacks a clearly

⁶¹ City of Helsinki (2022) [The City of Helsinki established principles for the ethical use of data and artificial intelligence](#)

⁶² [Helsinki Innovation Districts](#)

⁶³ Helsinki Smart Region; Helsinki-Uusimaa Regional Council (2022) [Helsinki Smart Region agenda](#).

⁶⁴ In 2024, Finland had the 4th highest share of individuals with basic IT skills of all the countries in the EU.

⁶⁵ Rinkkala, M. et al. (2019) [Internationally significant innovation and growth ecosystems in Finland](#)

⁶⁶ UNESCO (2025) Research and Development Expenditure (% of GDP). Available from [World Bank](#).

⁶⁷ *Ibid.* Available from [World Bank](#).

⁶⁸ EU (2024) [Assessment of the instruments, deliverables, results and impact of university business cooperation](#)

⁶⁹ Karkkonen, K. (2020) [Obstacles to growth for high technology SMEs in Finland](#)

structured and easily accessible SME support system, which can restrict startups' ability to secure growth finance, including venture capital. Without the skills and networks required to access VC funding, many Finnish tech SMEs struggle to scale.

B.23 Research by McKinsey⁷⁰ identifies a number of **cultural factors that stifle the business ecosystem in Finland**. They find that many Finnish companies do not set growth targets, or set ambitions that are insufficient to drive rapid expansion and innovation. Businesses also tend to deploy capital conservatively, often prioritising share buy-backs or debt repayment over investment in R&D. In addition, Finnish business leaders are sometimes characterised as lacking the visionary leadership needed to drive long-term growth and transformation.

Edinburgh and Glasgow

Background and context

B.24 Edinburgh and Glasgow are Scotland's two largest cities and form the eastern and western anchors of the Scottish Central Belt. In 2024, the combined population of the two city regions was approximately 1.2m, while the wider Central Belt had a population of around 2.5m⁷¹.

B.25 The Central Belt hosts a number of established startup and research strengths, most notably in FinTech and GreenTech⁷²: this case study focuses primarily on FinTech.

B.26 The FinTech cluster is both sizeable and expanding. In 2024, the sector was estimated to employ approximately 11k people, representing year-on-year growth of 8%⁷³. By the end of 2025, there were around 260 FinTech SMEs, a 10% increase on the previous year, which collectively raised £1.1bn in investment during 2025⁷⁴. This accounted for 40% of all FinTech investment raised in Scotland since 2018. Beyond SMEs, Edinburgh hosts approximately 1,200 financial services businesses, including major international firms such as J.P. Morgan, BlackRock, Royal London and Phoenix Group⁷⁵. Similarly, Glasgow is the UK's third largest financial centre, with large financial firms including Barclays, J.P. Morgan, Santander, Axa, and Zurich Insurance⁷⁶, alongside the government-owned Students Loans Company. The existence and significance of the Edinburgh–Glasgow FinTech cluster was recognised in the Kalifa Review of UK Fintech (2020), which identified it as having the third-highest number of FinTech businesses outside London and the Pennines (Manchester/Leeds)⁷⁷.

B.27 The FinTech cluster builds on a long-standing tradition of financial services in Scotland. The Bank of Scotland was founded in 1695, followed by the Royal Bank of Scotland in 1727. The

⁷⁰ Maksimainen, J. *et al.* (2025) [Seizing Finland's growth opportunity](#)

⁷¹ ONS (2025) Population estimates

⁷² Codebase (2025) [Edinburgh Shaping the Future of Innovation](#)

⁷³ Data Driven Innovation (2025) [Employment growth continues for Fintech Scotland cluster](#)

⁷⁴ FinTech Scotland (2025) [The Delivery and Impact of the FinTech Scotland Cluster in 2025](#)

⁷⁵ Innovate UK (2025) [Edinburgh and South East Scotland City Region Innovation Action Plan](#)

⁷⁶ FinTech Scotland (n.d.) [Fintech in Glasgow](#)

⁷⁷ HM Treasury (2021) [The Kalifa Review of UK FinTech](#)

1707 Act of Union enabled Scottish banking institutions to operate outside England's more restrictive regulatory framework, supporting the emergence of Edinburgh as a major financial centre⁷⁸. A number of financial innovations originated in the Scottish Central Belt, including overdrafts, life insurance and pensions⁷⁹.

Enabling factors

- B.28 The cluster benefits from a dedicated strategic cluster management organisation, 'FinTech Scotland'.** This independent body supports cluster development through facilitating collaboration, connecting firms with investors and international networks, producing research and thought leadership, and engaging with global FinTech ecosystems⁸⁰. FinTech Scotland is supported by financial services firms, universities and Scottish Enterprise.
- B.29 The FinTech ecosystem is further underpinned by a range of aligned research centres and institutes across the Central Belt.** These include the Financial Regulation Innovation Lab at the University of Strathclyde; the FinTech and Financial Services cluster within the University of Edinburgh's Centre for Data, Culture and Society; and the Centre of Excellence in Digital Trust and Distributed Ledger Technology at Edinburgh Napier University. In addition, the University of Edinburgh Business School hosts an annual Financial Technology conference.
- B.30 A range of policies, strategies and development frameworks also support cluster growth.** For example, FinTech is identified as a priority sector in the Edinburgh and South East Scotland Innovation Plan⁸¹ and is recognised as the UK's third-largest FinTech sector in commissioned research on sector support⁸². At the national level, FinTech is included within the eight 'high-growth industries' identified in the UK Industrial Strategy, and the UK Government's Financial Services Growth and Competitiveness Strategy explicitly references the strength of financial services and FinTech activity in Edinburgh and Glasgow⁸³. In 2022, FinTech Scotland published a roadmap for research and innovation in the Scottish FinTech sector covering the period to 2031, which has since guided its strategic activities⁸⁴.
- B.31** There is also an established, albeit relatively small, skills pipeline supporting the cluster. Of the ten UK master's-level courses specifically focused on FinTech in 2021, five were delivered by universities located within the Scottish Central Belt⁸⁵.

⁷⁸ Perman, R. (2022) *The Rise and Fall of the City of Money*

⁷⁹ *Ibid*

⁸⁰ FinTech Scotland, [About Us](#)

⁸¹ Innovate UK (2025) [Edinburgh and South East Scotland City Region Innovation Action Plan](#)

⁸² HM Treasury (2021) [The Kalifa Review of UK FinTech](#)

⁸³ UK Government (2024) [Financial Services Growth and Competitiveness Strategy](#)

⁸⁴ FinTech Scotland (2022) [FinTech Research & Innovation Roadmap 2021-31](#)

⁸⁵ Institute of Coding (2021) [The Digital Skills Gaps in the Fintech Industry](#)

Limiting factors

B.32 There is limited evidence specific to constraints affecting the FinTech cluster in the Scottish Central Belt. As a result, this section draws on wider evidence relating to constraints on the UK FinTech sector and the Scottish technology sector more broadly.

Factors limiting the growth of the UK FinTech sector

B.33 Access to finance (and business support) is identified by FinTech founders as the principal barrier to growth across firms of all sizes⁸⁶. Despite the UK government attempting to facilitate greater access to private finance, a growing proportion of FinTech SMEs have chosen to list outside the UK in recent years⁸⁷.

B.34 **Regulatory and compliance requirements also present a significant constraint.** The UK's detailed and highly structured financial services regulatory framework can create substantial delays for FinTech firms pursuing innovative business models, as approvals are required from the Financial Conduct Authority⁸⁸. In a 2025 survey of FinTech founders, 40% cited regulatory processes as a major barrier to growth⁸⁹.

Factors limiting the growth of the Scottish tech sector

B.35 **Technology firms in Scotland face persistent skills shortages, with many workplaces lacking core digital capabilities⁹⁰.** This shortage has contributed to heightened competition for certain roles, placing upward pressure on wages and potentially limiting the ability of SMEs to recruit the talent required for expansion. However, there is some evidence of improvement: the Scottish Government's 2024 Employer Skills Survey reported that the share of businesses with skills gaps identifying digital skills as part of those gaps had fallen to 31%, down from levels observed in 2020⁹¹.

⁸⁶ Fintech founders (2025) [2025 Annual Survey](#)

⁸⁷ HM Treasury (2021) [The Kalifa Review of UK FinTech](#)

⁸⁸ Startup Coalition (2025) [A Growth Vision for Fintech](#)

⁸⁹ Fintech founders (2025) [2025 Annual Survey](#)

⁹⁰ Skills Development Scotland (2022) [Digital Economy Skills Action Plan 2023-2028](#)

⁹¹ Scottish Government (2025) [Employer Skills Survey 2024 – Scotland](#)

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